

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Correlating Code Smells and Refactorings in the Elixir functional language

Institutions: DCC/ICEx/UFMG and DPI/CCE/UFV

Responsible researchers:

- Prof. Lucas Vegi (lucas.vegi@ufv.br)

Assistant Professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFV

- Prof. Marco Túlio Valente (mtov@dcc.ufmg.br)

Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand developers' perspectives on the ability of refactoring strategies for Elixir to remove code smells from programs implemented in this language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception of code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir (i.e., the completeness of the removals).

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 60 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research or the ethical aspects of this study: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucas.vegi@ufv.br.

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Avançar

Página 1 de 4

Limpar formulário

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

Select your country: *

Your city: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

[Voltar](#)

[Avançar](#)

Página 2 de 4 [Limpar formulário](#)

Nunca envie senhas pelo Google Formulários.

Este conteúdo não foi criado nem aprovado pelo Google. - [Entre em contato com o proprietário do formulário](#) - [Termos de Serviço](#) - [Política de Privacidade](#)

Este formulário parece suspeito? [Denunciar](#)

Google Formulários

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Perceptions on code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir

In previous studies, we cataloged [35 code smells](#) and [82 refactorings](#) tailored for Elixir. **In the present work, we are proposing practical guidelines for removing code smells in Elixir using sequences of refactorings specific to the language.**

For each code smell you are asked to evaluate, we will present the refactorings useful for its removal and explain their specific applications. These refactorings are listed in the order in which they should be performed when they are part of a sequence of operations. Specifically, when a refactoring should be applied on its own, it is listed with a bullet point (i.e., •). Conversely, when a refactoring is part of a sequence of operations, it is numbered to indicate its order (e.g., 1., 2., etc.).

Therefore, based on your experience, please answer the following questions for each presented smell:

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings removes this smell?

- Please rate the degree to which the refactoring sequence removes the code smell
- (1 = the refactoring sequence absolutely does not help remove the smell; 5 = the refactoring sequence completely removes the smell)

Notes:

- Each smell and refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link with code examples.

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Untested polymorphic behaviors\]](#) smell? *

This smell refers to a function with generic, protocol-dependent parameters but without guards to verify its behavior. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Introduce overloading\]](#): We can use this refactoring to transform a simple polymorphic function into a multi-clause function, where each clause of the function is responsible for handling one of the supported data types.
 2. [\[Folding against a function definition\]](#): After transforming a polymorphic function into a multi-clause function, we can use this refactoring to delegate part of the processing within a clause's body to calls of other clauses of the same function.
- [\[Typing parameters and return values\]](#): Another improvement possibility for code suffering from this code smell is to use this refactoring to document a polymorphic function, making it clear which data types it supports.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Dynamic atom creation\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a function creates *atoms* in an uncontrolled and dynamic way, which can negatively affect memory management. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Extract function\]](#): We can replace a call to the function *String.to_atom/1* with an explicit conversion. To do this, we can use this refactoring on the calls to *String.to_atom/1*, creating a new function. This new function should take a *string* as a parameter and convert it to an *atom*. The body of this function should include a conditional to check the content of the *string*. Depending on its content, the function will return a different *atom* directly.
2. [\[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter\]](#): After extracting a new function for explicit conversions from *strings* to *atoms*, we can use this refactoring to transform the function into a multi-clause function, where each clause is responsible for returning one of the possible converted *atoms*.
- [\[Folding against a function definition\]](#): If there is already a function in the module responsible for performing the explicit conversion of a *string* to an *atom* (e.g., a function extracted for this purpose at a different point in the same module), we can replace a call to *String.to_atom/1* with a call to that function.
1. [\[Introduce a temporary duplicate definition\]](#): Another alternative to refactor this code is to first duplicate the line where the function *String.to_atom/1* is called to create an *atom* dynamically. The new line should replace the call to *String.to_atom/1* with a call to *String.to_existing_atom/1*. This will ensure that string-to-atom conversions only map the *strings* to *atoms* already in memory. To enable this type of mapping, a suggestion is to create a *list* of these possible *atoms* within the function where this refactoring was applied.
2. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): After duplicating and modifying the duplicated line, we can eliminate the original line where the call to *String.to_atom/1* occurred.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\["Use" instead of "import"\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a module relies on "use" to declare dependencies even though an "import" would be sufficient. Typically, "use" implies tighter coupling with the target module. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Introduce import\]](#): When a "use" directive is unnecessarily used to establish a dependency between two modules, it can lead to unwanted propagation of internal dependencies from module A to module B. To remove this smell, we can initially replace a "use" directive with an "import" or "alias" directive. For this, we can first use this refactoring, which will create a more superficial dependency in module B with module A.
2. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): After adding the "import" directive, we should remove the "use" directive using this refactoring.
- [\[Alias expansion\]](#): Optionally, if the directive used to replace "use" is an "alias" and it is in the multi-alias format (e.g., *alias Foo.Bar.{Baz, Boom}*), we can use this refactoring, thus providing an improvement in code readability and traceability.
- [\[Remove import attributes\]](#): Optionally, if after replacing "use" with "import" we identify that a module is excessively importing other modules to the point of impairing readability—making it difficult to identify the origin of the functions it calls—we can perform this refactoring to some unnecessary imports. After that, we will then call the functions from the removed "imports" by their fully-qualified names.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Code organization by process\]](#) smell? *

This smell refers to code that is unnecessarily organized by processes. A process itself does not represent a code smell, but it should only be used to model runtime properties (e.g., concurrency, access to shared resources, event scheduling). When a process is used for code organization, it can create bottlenecks in the system. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Remove processes\]](#): When code unnecessarily uses a process for organizational purposes where a simple module with functions would suffice, this refactoring can be used to remove the unnecessary concurrent processes and replace them with regular Elixir modules.
2. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): When we transform a process into a regular Elixir module, some functions that previously implemented process callbacks (e.g., *GenServer*) may become unnecessary and can therefore be removed using this refactoring.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Large class\]](#) smell? *

Although Elixir does not support classes, functions can be grouped by *modules* in a similar way. When a module is not cohesive, it deals with multiple distinct business rules, tending to have many functions and lines of code, becoming large. This makes maintenance difficult. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Splitting a large module\]](#): When a module does the work of two or more, it becomes large, poorly cohesive, and difficult to maintain. In these cases, we should split this module into several new ones, moving to each new module only the attributes and functions with purposes related to their respective goals.
 2. [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): In some cases, after splitting an original module into several smaller and more cohesive modules, the name of the original module can no longer make sense, providing an opportunity to also apply this refactoring.
- [\[Behaviour extraction\]](#): This operation is helpful if it's necessary to have a list of operations and behaviors that client modules can reuse, thus reducing their sizes.
 - [\[Moving a definition\]](#): When a function is defined in module *A* but is more suited to the responsibilities of module *B*, we can move it to *B* to reduce the size of *A*.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Primitive obsession\]](#) smell? *

This code smell can be felt when Elixir basic types (e.g., *integer*, *float*, and *string*) are abusively used in function parameters and code variables, rather than creating specific composite data types (e.g., *protocols*, *structs*, and *@type*) that can better represent a domain. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Grouping parameters in tuple\]](#): If primitive/basic type values are used in function parameters to inadequately represent more complex real-world abstractions, you can initially apply this refactoring to group them.
 2. [\[From tuple to struct\]](#): A *tuple* used to group parameters can eventually be replaced by a *struct*, thus creating a more robust data structure for this purpose.
- [\[Add type declarations and contracts\]](#): We can use this refactoring to generate a type specification to replace primitive/basic values.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the **[Long function]** smell? *

Poorly cohesive function, made up of too many lines of code that group together many different responsibilities that could be separated into smaller functions with a single responsibility each. Generally, any function longer than ten lines should make you start asking questions. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- **[Extract function]:** If a comment is needed to explain some part of the function body, this refactoring can be used to create a new function to be called at the location of this comment, thus decreasing the size of the original function.
 - **[Transform nested "if" statements into a "cond"]:** If a function uses many nested *if* conditionals, this can greatly increase its size. In these cases, we can use this refactoring to decrease the size of the function.
 - **[Folding against a function definition]:** If a function performs operations that can be delegated to other existing functions, it may become unnecessarily long. In these cases, we can use this refactoring to reduce the size of the original function.
 - **[Remove dead code]:** If a function contains code that is no longer used, it may become unnecessarily long. In these cases we can use this refactoring to reduce the size of the original function.
 - **[Simplifying checks by using truthness condition]:** When we know that a given data item can be *nil* and we need to return a default value if it is indeed *nil*, we can use this refactoring to reduce the number of lines in a function while maintaining clean and self-explanatory code.
 - **[Generalise a function definition]:** When different functions have equivalent expression structures, these equivalent expressions can be generalized into a new higher-order function, thus reducing the size of the original functions.
 - **[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter]:** When a function has many branches in its body that depend on values received as parameters, it can become unnecessarily long. We can use this refactoring to create short multi-clauses for the original function, where each clause handles a different branch.
 - **[Replace pipeline with a function]:** When a function is unnecessarily long due to a pipeline of function calls that can be replaced by a single call, we can use this refactoring to address the issue.
 - **[Default value for an absent key in a Map]:** A function can have its number of lines reduced by using this refactoring to replace the use of *if* statements that check the return of *Map.has_key?/2* with a call to the *Map.get/3* function.
 - **[Defining a subset of a Map]:** When a function is unnecessarily long because it manually creates a subset of a *Map* by individually accessing each of the desired key/value pairs, we can use this refactoring to delegate this task to a call to *Map.take/2*.
 - **[Pipeline using "with"]:** When a function uses nested conditionals solely to control a sequence of function calls, it can become long. By using this refactoring, we can make the function more idiomatic and reduce its number of lines of code.
 - **[Remove redundant last clause in "with"]:** This refactoring can reduce the number of lines of code used by a *with* statement and consequently shorten the size of the function that uses this statement.
 - **[Modifying keys in a Map]:** When a function is unnecessarily long because it manually replaces a *Map* key with a new key using *Map.get/2*, *Map.put/2*, and *Map.delete/2* functions together, we can use this refactoring to delegate this task to a call to *Map.new/2*, thus significantly reducing the volume of lines of code.
 - **[Remove nested conditional statements in function calls]:** When a function uses unnecessary nested conditional statements, it can become long and less readable. In such circumstances, we can use this refactoring to replace the unnecessary nested conditional statements with less bulky code that maintains the same behavior, thus making the code simpler and more readable.
 - **[Splitting a definition]:** When the refactoring [Merging multiple definitions] is used carelessly, there is a risk of creating a long function. In such cases, we can undo this operation using the present refactoring, thereby generating smaller, separate functions.
 - **[Merging match expressions into a list pattern]:** If a function uses many lines of code with expressions that assign results to temporary variables but can be replaced by a single *list* generated through pattern matching, we can use this refactoring to reduce the size of the function.
1. **[Convert nested conditionals to pipeline]:** When a function uses nested conditionals solely to control a sequence of function calls, it can become long. By using this refactoring, we can give the function a more functional appearance and reduce the number of lines of code.
 2. **[Replace function call with raw value in a pipeline start]:** When using the previous refactoring to remove this smell, we may also encounter an opportunity to apply the present operation, making the refactored code more idiomatic.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

[Voltar](#)

[Avançar](#)

Página 3 de 4 [Limpar formulário](#)

Nunca envie senhas pelo Google Formulários.

Este conteúdo não foi criado nem aprovado pelo Google. - [Entre em contato com o proprietário do formulário](#) - [Termos de Serviço](#) - [Política de Privacidade](#)

Este formulário parece suspeito? [Denunciar](#)

Google Formulários

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Final remarks

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

- Yes
- No

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

[Voltar](#)

[Enviar](#)

Página 4 de 4

[Limpar formulário](#)

Nunca envie senhas pelo Google Formulários.

Este conteúdo não foi criado nem aprovado pelo Google. - [Entre em contato com o proprietário do formulário](#) - [Termos de Serviço](#) - [Política de Privacidade](#)

Este formulário parece suspeito? [Denunciar](#)

Google Formulários

